

Special Session on: OPTIMIZATION DRIVEN ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN OF STRUCTURES

According to UNEP, the building sector is estimated to be worth 10% of the global GDP and employs 111 million people. In addition, buildings use about 40% of global energy, 40% of global resources and emit approximately 33% of global GHG emissions. Finally, the fact that people today spend, on average, more than 80% of their time indoors, enhances its social importance. All above indicate the necessity to optimize building design.

Architects usually name “optimal design” the choice among a very limited set of design alternatives, dictated by their experience and intuition. However, modern design of structures requires one to account for a great number of criteria deriving from multiple disciplines, often of conflicting nature. The vast number of alternative choices enhances the possibility of arriving at an optimum with the incorporation of smart, automatic tools in the design process, further guiding designer’s intuition.

Moreover optimization tools are usually referred to engineering approaches to design, while architectural approaches are commonly referred to form and esthetic definitions.

Currently the developing of more and more computational efficient software tools able to be faster and more important easier to be used, offers a new way to integrate structural optimization in preliminary architectural design at an early phase.

This Special Session is aimed at presenting the recent state-of-the-art work on shape and topology optimization techniques in computer aided architectural design, new formulations that correspond to real-life applications and novel developments on the optimal multi-disciplinary architectural design. Of particular interest is the combination of criteria deriving from structural mechanics, eco-design, bioclimatic design and acoustic performance.

Some Indicative topics are:

- New design optimization algorithms
- Shape and topology optimization in conceptual architectural design
- Criteria, constraints and interpretation step
- Modelling, analysis and design of optimized structural systems
- Multidisciplinary architectural design optimization.
- Bioclimatic building design improved through performance optimization
- Optimal design for acoustic performance
- Optimized hybrid kinetic and adaptive structures

It is believed that the Special Session will enable the exchange of experience and develop ideas for further research in this important scientific field.

Organized by:

Nikos D. Lagaros (National Technical University Athens, Greece, nlagaros@central.ntua.gr)

Giuseppe Carlo Marano (Fuzhou University, China, marano@fzu.edu.cn)

Bruno Briseghella (Fuzhou University, China, bruno@fzu.edu.cn)